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Title: Nature, Dyscivilization, and Governance: A Processual Approach to Protected Natural Areas in Latin America

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Abstract: This paper revisits the theoretical contributions of Abram de Swaan and Norbert Elias to examine the complex interdependencies between nature and dyscivilization processes, specifically within the context of Protected Natural Areas (PNAs) in Mexico and Argentina. It characterises the recurring features of these PNAs and their relationships with various governmental management models. By introducing and discussing the concept of 'compartmentalisation,' the authors provides a framework for future comparative analyses of PNAs. The methodological foundation of the proposal is grounded in the authors' ethnographic research conducted across various PNAs in Mexico and Argentina, complemented by a comprehensive compilation and analysis of existing research and official management plans. The paper concludes by identifying the common characteristics of the PNAs under study, offering a discussion on how the concept of compartmentalisation can reshape our understanding of their governance and the broader civilising processes. It reveals that PNAs, far from being static entities, are continually model by ongoing social struggles, including issues of sovereignty, indigenous rights, and state control over national borders and natural resources. These areas not only serve as environmental sanctuaries but also as arenas of conflict and negotiation between the consolidation of national states and local communities. The findings underscore the importance of adopting a processual approach to PNA management—one that acknowledges the intricate socio-environmental challenges, the shifting power dynamics, and the broader implications for civilising processes in both regional and global contexts.

Keywords: Argentina, Mexico, Discivilization, Compartmentalization, Protected Natural Areas.